

VISTA AI Risk Assessment Toolkit

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VISTA AI Risk Assessment Toolkit

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1. Executive summary

The VISTA AI Risk Assessment Toolkit supports Trusted Research Environments (TREs) to safely enable projects that train machine learning (ML) models on sensitive data. As ML becomes increasingly used across health, social care and economic domains, organisations must be able to assess and manage the privacy risks that arise when models learn from real world sensitive information.

This toolkit provides a clear and practical process for identifying and mitigating those risks. It builds on the widely used Five Safes framework¹ and aligns with recognised guidance including RELEASE-AI², the GRAIMATTER recommendations³ and the Information Commissioner's Office (ICO) AI and Data Protection Risk Toolkit⁴, helping TREs take an evidence-based approach to evaluating AI projects.

The toolkit comprises four main components:

1. **Researcher AI Questionnaire:** Outlining the model type, data used and plans for testing and release (Appendix 1)
2. **A Structured Risk Assessment Form:** Completed during feasibility review to identify privacy risks and appropriate controls (Appendix 2)
3. **A Set of Actionable Controls:** Providing safeguards from secure access requirements to model testing standards (Section 4)
4. **A Released Trained Model Registry:** Allowing TREs to record model details, support transparency and manage secondary disclosure risks (Appendix 3)

A key feature is the integration of SACRO-ML⁵, which enables TREs to test whether a trained model could leak sensitive information before it leaves the secure environment. Embedding these checks within standard workflows helps TREs support innovative research while protecting privacy and ensuring public benefit.

This version 1 toolkit is designed for TRE operational teams and governance bodies supporting ML model training on sensitive data. It complements existing governance processes, including Patient & Public Involvement (PPI) review, and is intended to evolve over time. As methods, risks and safeguards for ML continue to develop, so too will this toolkit. We welcome feedback from TRE teams, researchers, and the public to help refine and strengthen future iterations.

Development of the toolkit has been informed by Patient and Public Involvement and Engagement (PPIE) through the Eastern England SDE (EE-SDE) Core Public Advisory Group (CPAG). Their insights ensured that the VISTA AI Risk Assessment Toolkit reflects public expectations around transparency, accountability and the responsible use of automation in health and care research.

This toolkit has been produced as part of the DARE UK Viable Implementation for SATRE⁶, SACRO⁷ and Tools for AI (VISTA) Early Adopter project. The VISTA programme aims to enable approved researchers to safely train and export ML and AI models from TREs and to prepare the health and care system for the responsible deployment of these models in NHS services. The toolkit represents an initial step in this wider ambition and will continue to be refined in collaboration with the TRE community as the project progresses.

2. Toolkit scope and users

2.1 ML architectural scope

This toolkit provides a governance framework to support TREs that wish to permit projects involving the training of machine learning (ML) models on sensitive data. It covers the full lifecycle of such projects (Figure 1), from the researcher's initial data access request, through feasibility assessment and data access approval, to model egress and project closure.

Figure 1: TRE Project Lifecycle stages – the primary stages in a TRE project, from applying for access, feasibility and governance and project setup, to results egress and project closure

A central component of the toolkit is SACRO-ML, which provides structured, evidence-based testing to assess whether training an ML model on sensitive data could lead to privacy disclosure. Its value lies in enabling TREs to generate direct, simulated evidence of disclosure risk, something that is rarely available through traditional governance processes. By incorporating SACRO-ML testing, TREs can make more confident, defensible decisions about whether a model can safely leave the secure environment.

SACRO-ML is currently designed to evaluate a defined set of model families. It supports:

- Classification models from scikit-learn, including models inheriting from `sklearn.base.BaseEstimator`
- A broad range of PyTorch models, enabling assessment of many deep learning architectures

For these model types, TREs can obtain quantifiable evidence about the risk of sensitive information being inferred or extracted from a trained model. SACRO-ML does not yet include model types such as large language models, generative architectures (e.g., GANs), reinforcement learning models, or highly bespoke pipelines that fall outside standard scikit-learn or PyTorch patterns.

TREs may still apply the wider principles of this toolkit to other model classes, but where SACRO-ML cannot be applied, the ability to produce simulated evidence of disclosure risk is limited. Each TRE must therefore determine, based on its own governance and regulatory requirements, whether model types not supported by SACRO-ML can be permitted and what additional safeguards would be required to ensure public benefit while protecting individual privacy.

SACRO-ML provides two complementary forms of privacy assessment:

- Ante-hoc testing, via the `SafeModel` wrapper, allowing researchers to identify potential disclosure vulnerabilities during model training
- Post-hoc testing, using model attack tools that enable airlock managers to run simulated privacy attacks on trained models before they are considered for egress

Together, these capabilities allow TREs to embed consistent, evidence-driven privacy checks into their existing workflows.

2.2 Toolkit contributors and audience

This toolkit has been developed collaboratively by airlock managers and research governance representatives from the EE-SDE team, with additional input from the SACRO-ML developers. It draws on the RELEASE-AI framework and the GRAIMATTER recommendations as its foundational guidance.

The primary audience for this toolkit is TRE operational teams, including airlock managers and research governance representatives who oversee data access applications and manage data and code egress from a TRE. It may also be valuable to data access committee (DAC) members, data controllers, and researchers, helping them understand the considerations involved in assessing the risks associated with training or validating machine learning models on sensitive data within a TRE.

3. ML disclosure risks

At the core of this toolkit is an assessment of whether an egressed model could be unintentionally prompted or intentionally attacked to reveal sensitive attributes, reconstruct identifiable patterns, or confirm an individual's presence in the training data. The following sections outline key categories of disclosure risk⁸ that may arise when training machine learning models on sensitive data, along with the indicators that can typically be identified at the feasibility stage. These Machine Learning Risks are assigned identifiers (MLRO-9) to support cross referencing throughout this document. This list is not exhaustive; as the field evolves and

community understanding of model-related disclosure risks continues to grow, we will remain actively engaged with domain experts and update the set of risks we monitor accordingly.

MLR01: Implicit Memorisation of Training Data⁹

Some models may unintentionally memorise rare, unique, or highly specific patterns found in the training dataset. This risk increases when researchers plan to use very high-capacity models, especially deep learning architectures, together with small datasets or datasets that contain rare conditions or very small subgroups. Memorisation is also more likely when long or intensive training regimes are proposed, or when the research involves sequence-based tasks. When these characteristics appear in the application, reviewers should consider the possibility that the model could store individual-level patterns that might later be reproduced.

MLR02: Extraction of Explicitly Stored Data¹⁰

Certain models store training samples, or derived representations of them, directly within the model. This is common in instance-based and kernel approaches such as k-Nearest Neighbours, Support Vector Machines, and case-based reasoning systems. When these architectures are proposed, there is an increased risk that identifiable records could be extracted from the trained model. Early identification of these model families during feasibility review allows TREs to anticipate the need for alternative methods or for strong disclosure-mitigation controls.

MLR03: Membership Inference Risk¹¹

Membership inference refers to the risk that an attacker could determine whether a specific person's data was included in the training dataset. This risk tends to be higher when the proposed dataset involves small cohorts or rare populations, or when the model is designed to return confidence scores or probability distributions that differ between individuals who were included in training and those who were not. Indicators such as overfitting, or planned use of highly calibrated prediction outputs, can also signal elevated membership-inference vulnerability.

MLR04: Attribute Inference Risk¹²

Attribute inference occurs when a model's outputs allow an attacker to deduce additional sensitive characteristics about an individual. This can happen even when the attribute in question is not part of the model's explicit output. The risk is greater when the training data contains highly correlated features, detailed demographic or clinical information, or complex relationships that the model may capture. Reviewers should take note when the modelling task or the dataset description suggests that apparently harmless outputs could reveal other personal attributes in practice.

MLR05: Model Inversion and Group Reconstruction^{13,14}

Some models, especially those that produce finely detailed or highly confident predictions, may be vulnerable to attacks that reconstruct features of individuals or small groups. This risk is most relevant when the training data contains homogenous or very small subgroups. In such cases, the patterns learned by the model can closely reflect the underlying individuals. Applications that describe very granular prediction tasks, or outputs that could isolate small subgroups, should be carefully examined for inversion risk.

MLR06: Non-Explainable or “Black Box” Models¹⁵

Models with limited interpretability are harder to assess for disclosure risk. This includes deep neural networks, large or complex architectures, and pipelines that provide little visibility into their internal logic. Low explainability makes it more difficult for TRE staff to understand whether disclosive patterns are embedded within the model, and it increases reliance on specialist evaluation techniques. Research plans that involve opaque model architectures should explain how disclosure risks will be evaluated despite the lack of transparency.

MLR07: Secondary Disclosure Through Multiple Model Releases

Even when individual models appear safe, releasing multiple trained models that are based on the same or overlapping data may create new disclosure risks. If researchers plan to export several models, conduct iterative refinements, or compare different models externally, there is a possibility that combined outputs could enable inference about the underlying training data. Feasibility reviewers must reject any plan which involves egressing a trained model more than once as there are no current mechanisms to reasonably assess the risk of secondary disclosure between models trained on the same input data.

4. Actionable controls

The risks associated with any proposed model development must be balanced against the expected public benefit. Models trained on sensitive data inherently carry some degree of disclosure risk, such as the potential for information about individuals to be inferred or misused if the model unintentionally reveals properties of the training data.

This section outlines the actionable controls that may be required for an approved project. These measures are designed to ensure that public benefit is realised while safeguarding individual privacy. The controls are aligned with the Five Safes framework (Figure 2) to clarify the aspects of the model creation and usage lifecycle. As with the risks described earlier, this set of controls is not exhaustive. Model governance is an evolving area, and we will continue to monitor advances in best practice, engage with the wider community, and update these controls as understanding of model-related risks and mitigations develops.

Figure 2: The Five Safes framework, which enable data services to provide safe research access to data

4.1 Safe People

- The model should only be accessible to authorised individuals. Access must be controlled through secure hosting and implemented using role-based access control (RBAC), ensuring that only named analysts, clinicians, or other approved personnel can interact with the model. It should not be publicly distributed or made available in a way that allows unrestricted use by anyone who discovers its location.

4.2 Safe Projects

- The intended outputs and use of the released model must remain aligned with the stated aims and public benefit case of the approved project.
- The model should ideally be distributed under a licence that explicitly restricts secondary use, including any unauthorised re-training or repurposing. A suitable licence with adequate protections and requirements may accompany the model if it is transferred beyond its initial hosting environment, where relevant.

4.3 Safe Data

- The model training process should incorporate appropriate suppression of rare values and aggregation strategies to limit the risk that training data include disclosive or uniquely identifying information.
- Where appropriate, the training process should consider the use of synthetic data¹⁶, fully anonymised datasets with documentation on fidelity, utility, and privacy characteristics, or differential privacy techniques during training and prediction, provided these measures do not compromise the intended public benefit.

4.4 Safe Settings

- The model training workflow should include systematic monitoring of training activity. This should include logging dataset versions, training configurations such as hyperparameters, and any incorporated pretrained components. This monitoring enables early identification and investigation of patterns that may elevate disclosure risk.
- The model must be hosted within a secure environment such as a TRE that enforces authenticated access and RBAC controlled query permissions. Hosting may occur within the TRE in which the model was originally trained or within another suitably accredited secure environment. Appropriate secure hosting should hold appropriate certifications such as the Digital Economy Act (DEA) processing accreditation¹⁷, ISO27001¹⁸, NHS Data Security Protection Toolkit¹⁹ or Standard Architecture for Trusted Research Environments (SATRE).
- The model inference interface must enforce strict query-type controls to prevent inappropriate or high-risk inputs. Only predefined categories of permitted queries should be accepted, and all incoming queries must be programmatically evaluated against these criteria. The interface should automatically sanitise queries that contain potentially identifying, unsupported, or otherwise sensitive content; where sanitisation is not possible, the query must be rejected. This control ensures that only safe and

context-appropriate interactions reach the model, reducing the likelihood of inadvertent disclosure or misuse. These controls may also include query rate limiting to restrict how many queries and how frequently an individual user can use the model.

4.5 Safe Outputs

- The model should undergo appropriate model disclosure risk assessment, for example through tools such as SACRO-ML, to estimate and evaluate upper bound disclosure risks.
- Model outputs should be subject to statistical disclosure control²⁰ to ensure they do not pose risks to individuals whose data contributed to training.
- Egress from the TRE should be tightly governed. Models should only be approved for egress if paired with other artefacts such as licensing documents, embedded watermarks or metadata, and appropriate explainability outputs that are assessed as safe for external use.

5. ML training risk assessment playbook

This toolkit provides procedures for six stages during the project lifecycle (Figure 3) to assess and manage the risks present when training ML models on sensitive data inside a TRE. These procedures are focused on risk management for ML training projects and are not intended to replace any other processes a TRE normally uses to assess a project for suitability or manage data egress risks and project closure processes.

Figure 3: The project lifecycle stages and processes needed for each stage.

These stages are:

5.1 Data Access Request (DAR)

The researcher needs to provide information about their project plan to support the risk assessment process. This should include information such as what type of model is going to be trained, the data pre-processing plans, model egress plans and other similar information. We have developed a Researcher AI Questionnaire comprising a set of questions which captures all the needed information for the Risk Assessment and Scoring process. These questions could be directly integrated into a TRE's Data Access Request form or provided as an appendix where relevant. A copy of the Researcher AI Questionnaire can be found in Appendix 1 including both the template and an example.

5.2 Project Feasibility

The Data Manager, or another suitably qualified subject matter expert, should review the information provided in the Data Access Request form, including all relevant details from Appendix 1: Researcher AI Questionnaire. Using this material, the reviewer can assess the feasibility and the risks associated with the machine learning (ML) training elements of the proposal. The reviewer should also identify any actionable controls necessary to mitigate any risks emerging from the plan. This assessment should result in:

- A risk score for the ML training plan
- A set of actionable controls to mitigate any identified risks

These outputs should be documented in a structured format for ease of review by others, such as the format provided in Appendix 2: AI Risk Assessment Form, which includes the template and an example.

This evaluation should be carried out alongside the reviewer's other project feasibility checks, such as ensuring the inclusion and exclusion criteria for the requested dataset are appropriate and that the requested attributes available to the TRE. As with all feasibility assessments, this process is expected to be iterative, with the researcher responding to feedback and refining their proposal to ensure an appropriate balance between scientific value and public benefit and the protection of individual privacy before the project is submitted for approval by the Data Access Committee (DAC).

5.3 Data Access Approval

The AI risk assessment and proposed actionable controls should be used alongside a DAC's existing baseline governance and assurance processes, including PPI review, to support their decision making and ensure there are appropriate stipulations added to the Data Access Agreement if identified as needed during the AI risk assessment process.

5.4 Code and Reference Data Ingress

All TREs following the Safe Settings principle (see section 4.4) from the Five-Safes Framework have existing baseline checks during data and code ingress. These are likely to involve human approval and Personally Identifiable Information (PII) scanning to confirm no unplanned sensitive data is being brought into the environment, and vulnerability scanning to ensure no security risks are being introduced. For an approved ML project, if code or reference data needs to be ingressed, it should be reviewed following the same process as any other code or data which may be ingressed into a TRE.

5.5 Intermediate results egress

All TREs following the Safe Outputs principle (see section 4.5) from the Five-Safes Framework are likely to have a statistical disclosure control process for egress of research outputs^{21,22}. Any intermediate research outputs during a ML training project lifecycle should be subject to these disclosure control checks. The trained model itself should only be egressed once at project closure due to secondary disclosure risk.

5.6 Egress and Project Closure

The trained ML model can only be egressed at project closure. Multiple egress events introduce significant secondary disclosure risk (see MLR07), so only a single egress is permitted at the end of the project.

To reduce the risk of rejection at the final disclosure review, TRE staff should maintain regular contact with the research team throughout the project. As the team's understanding of the data evolves, the TRE can verify that the detail of the project remains relevant to the risk assessment conducted at project feasibility, if needed, update the risk assessment and agree any additional actionable controls. Where suitable, using ante-hoc testing via SACRO-ML's SafeModel package can help mitigate some risks by identifying possible disclosure issues before a model is trained, but ongoing updates to the project plan remain essential.

The egress review process for a trained model includes the following steps:

1. **Privacy Risk Assessment:** Use the relevant^{23,24} SACRO-ML simulated privacy attack modules to assess the risk of data disclosure from the trained model
2. **Statistical Disclosure Control:** Apply the TRE's standard SDC practices to review the model output and any associated artefacts (e.g., validation metrics) to confirm they can be safely released
3. **Actionable Controls Review:** Verify that any required controls specified in the initial risk assessment are in place, such as:
 - I. Appropriate license text
 - II. Confirmation of hosting environment accreditation
 - III. Availability of role base access controls on hosting environment
 - IV. Availability of suitable interface to apply query type restrictions

The model and associated artefacts may be egressed only if all checks are passed. At that point, the model should also be added to the TRE's model registry (see Appendix 3: Released Trained Model Registry²⁵ for template and example). The registry provides transparency on models trained within the TRE and the types of data used and supports future oversight and audit activities.

6. In summary

This toolkit provides a structured, evidence-based approach to assessing and managing the risks that arise when training machine learning (ML) models on sensitive data within a TRE. It supports TREs to enable high-value, innovative research while ensuring that individual privacy and public trust remain central to decision-making.

The framework brings together three key components: a clear process for identifying disclosure risks associated with different model types and training plans; a set of actionable controls aligned to the Five Safes; and practical assessment tools, including the Researcher AI Questionnaire, the ML Training Risk Assessment Form, and the Released Model Registry. Together, these enable TREs to evaluate proposals consistently, document decisions transparently, and ensure that any model approved for egress has undergone rigorous review.

A core strength of this toolkit is its integration of SACRO-ML, which provides ante-hoc and post-hoc simulated evidence of potential disclosure from trained models. Embedding these checks into TRE workflows enhances assurance and supports defensible governance, particularly as ML techniques evolve.

Both the risks and the controls presented here are non-exhaustive. The landscape of ML-related privacy threats and mitigations continues to develop rapidly, and we are committed to remaining closely connected to the TRE, privacy, and ML governance communities. The toolkit will be updated as new evidence, methods, and best practice standards emerge.

By adopting this approach, TREs can confidently support innovative ML research while maintaining robust protections for individuals and ensuring that public benefit remains the guiding principle in all decision-making.

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Glossary

Five Safes – A widely used framework for designing and assessing safe access to sensitive data across five dimensions: Safe People, Safe Projects, Safe Settings, Safe Data and Safe Outputs (considered together to achieve “safe use”)

Airlock Manager - A data security role in Trusted Research Environments, responsible for reviewing and approving data transfers in and out of the TRE.

Ante-hoc / Post-hoc Testing – Testing during model training vs after model training.

CPAG – Core Public Advisory Group, the patient and public advisory group established for the Eastern England Secure Data Environment.

DAC – Data Access Committee, the group of governance, subject matter experts and members of the public who review and make access decisions for a given TRE.

DAR – Data Access Request, the form or document completed by a researcher to describe their research question and data needs so an access decision can be made for a given TRE.

DEA accreditation (2017) - Digital Economy Act (2017) accreditation demonstrates that an institution meets a set of criteria that individuals, organisations and research projects laid out in the Research Code of Practice and Accreditation Criteria.

EE-SDE – Eastern England Secure Data Environment, a platform for secure, controlled access to de-personalised patient data for research.

ISO/IEC 27001:2022 – The international standard that sets requirements for establishing, implementing, maintaining and continually improving an Information Security Management System (ISMS) to manage information security risks.

ML – Machine Learning, statistical algorithms that can learn from data.

NHS DSPT – NHS Data Protection and Security Toolkit is a online self-assessment tool for health and care organizations to measure performance against the National Data Guardian’s 10 data security standards and GDPR requirements.

PII – Personally Identifiable Information, refers to any data that can be used to identify a specific person, including health information that is linked to their identity.

PPI(E) – Patient and Public Involvement (and Engagement) is the active partnership between researchers and the public to shape health research.

RBAC (Role-Based Access Control) – Restricting access based on user roles.

SACRO – Semi-Automated Checking of Research Outputs, is a semi-automated system of tools nested in the EE-SDE for checks on research outputs. It can enhance oversight and auditing for airlock managers.

SACRO-ML – Semi-Automated Checking of Research Outputs and Machine Learning, includes support for the managing of Statistical Disclosure Control of trained Machine Learning models engaged within the Secure Data Environment.

SATRE – Standardised Architecture for Trusted Research Environments, is a community-driven specification for the UK and beyond for building and operating Trusted Research Environments.

SDC – Statistical Disclosure Control, is a set of techniques used by airlock managers, or data custodians more broadly, to prevent the re-identification of individuals or entities in released data.

TRE – Trusted Research Environments, or otherwise Secure Data Environments are highly secure and controlled digital platforms allowing approved researchers access to sensitive, de-identified data for public interest research. These platforms house data and negate the need to move data around.

VISTA – Viable Implementation of SATRE, SACRO and Tools for AI, is the Early Adopter project funded by DARE UK, aimed towards delivering tools to enhance Statistical Disclosure Checking, support in TREs for Machine Learning, and also for establishing a benchmarking standard for Trusted Research Environments.

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Appendix 1 - Research AI Questionnaire

VISTA AI RISK ASSESSMENT TOOLKIT (Version 1)

[These questions could be directly integrated into a TRE’s Data Access Request form or provided as an appendix where relevant].

This form collects information about your planned machine learning approach so we can understand any potential risks related to data disclosure, privacy, model training, and model quality. The questions focus on your current intentions regarding data use, model design, training processes, evaluation methods, risk mitigation approaches, and plans for model egress.

We recognise that these are early plans and that iteration is expected. Your responses should outline your intended approach based on what you know now. Once a project is approved and you have access to the data, you may refine your methods, and we will be able to discuss and agree any changes as your understanding of the dataset develops.

The information you provide will be used to carry out an ML specific feasibility and risk assessment. This assessment will support the data access decision-making process and may also inform recommended controls on training, evaluation, and egress to help ensure the privacy of individuals and the reliability and safety of any models developed within the TRE.

All questions are mandatory.

<p>1. Summarise the type(s) of model you intend to bring into the platform and the licensing associated with them.</p> <p><i>Please describe the model type(s) you will use (e.g., regression models, classical ML models, deep learning architectures, foundation models). Include any information about model provenance, licensing arrangements, and intellectual-property considerations. If a system card or model card exists, please provide it, as it helps us understand general risks associated with the model family and its intended use.</i></p>	
<p>2. Describe the input data your model requires and the outputs you expect it to produce.</p> <p><i>Please explain the types of input data needed to train or fine-tune the model, including the level</i></p>	

<p><i>of specificity to individuals and any plans to suppress or transform rare or identifying values. How many data points are required? Describe the structure and type of model outputs (e.g., numeric predictions, risk scores, text). If your outputs could potentially reveal sensitive information, please detail how this risk will be managed.</i></p>	
<p>3. Summarise your approach to data processing, creating training and test data, and data cleaning.</p> <p><i>Please describe how you will preprocess and clean the data, including approaches to handling missingness or errors. Explain how you will construct training, validation, and test datasets and ensure robust separation between them. Will you use cross-validation? Please also outline any processes to detect and prevent data leakage, such as checks for duplicated individuals or near-duplicate records across dataset splits. Describe how you will identify and minimise bias in the training and test data, and whether the pipeline applies suppression or obfuscation of rare values.</i></p>	
<p>4. Summarise your approach to model training, including training duration, intensity, and safeguards against memorisation of sensitive data.</p> <p><i>Please describe the structure of your training regime (e.g., number of epochs, batch size, learning-rate schedules) and how these choices balance performance with generalisation.</i></p>	

<p><i>Explain how you will monitor for overfitting during training and whether you will conduct memorisation or extraction-resistance testing. Describe any checks for duplicated or near-identical records that could encourage memorisation. What methods will you use to minimise the risk of the model learning or retaining rare or identifying values (e.g., regularisation, noise injection, differential privacy, early stopping)?</i></p>	
<p>5. Summarise your plan to ensure the trained model is accurate, robust and capable or delivering the stated benefits?</p> <p><i>Please describe your model testing strategy and evaluation strategy, including the metrics, benchmarks and validation datasets, any robustness or fairness assessments. Please provide information about the base model(s) including provenance and groups involved in their creation; training method and tuning approach (if different from what is described above); parameter count; published performance metrics (if any exist). Explain how you will ensure the model remains generalisable and avoids overfitting during any further finetuning stages. Also provide information about where the base model has been sourced from, how it was tuned and what group(s) was involved in creating it. How many parameters has the base model been trained on? What performance benchmarks exist for the proposed base model(s). Describe your plans to avoid the model overfitting to the training data.</i></p>	
<p>6. Describe your own assessment of any disclosure or privacy risks associated with your approach?</p>	

<p><i>Please describe any disclosure or other risks associated with your model and your plan to mitigate these risks to ensure the public benefit described in your data access request form is realised without compromising the privacy of the individuals whose data is used to train the model.</i></p>	
<p>7. Summarise your ingress, egress and ongoing hosting plans for the trained model and any accompanying artefacts.</p> <p><i>Please describe what if any data or model components you will need to ingress into the TRE and then model components or additional information you will need to egress from the TRE, and whether any associated artefacts represent a disclosure risk and how you plan to mitigate those risks. Explain where the model will be hosted long-term, how it will be licensed or distributed, and what access controls will be applied. Describe how you will manage future querying of the model to prevent misuse or leakage of sensitive information the model may have been exposed to.</i></p>	

Example AI Researcher Questionnaire - Diabetes Risk Prediction Using Aggregated Clinical Features

Example answers for the AI Researcher Questionnaire based on a project to train a ML model to predict the likelihood of type 2 diabetes based on routinely collected clinical data.

<p>Summarise the type(s) of model you intend to bring into the platform and the licensing associated with them.</p> <p><i>Please describe the model type(s) you will use (e.g., regression models, classical ML models, deep learning architectures, foundation models). Include any information about model provenance, licensing arrangements, and intellectual-property considerations. If a system card or model card exists, please provide it, as it helps us understand general risks associated with the model family and its intended use.</i></p>	<p>The project proposes to develop supervised machine learning models to predict the likelihood of Type 2 diabetes using routinely collected clinical data within the Secure Data Environment (SDE).</p> <p>The primary modelling approach will use ensemble tree-based methods, specifically Random Forest-type classifiers. These models are selected due to their ability to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Capture non-linear relationships between demographic and clinical variables • Model interactions across multiple feature groups • Handle heterogeneous feature types (demographic and aggregated clinical counts) <p>Two modelling configurations are anticipated:</p>
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	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. A baseline ensemble model using demographic and limited clinical summary features. 2. A richer feature ensemble model incorporating aggregated counts of healthcare visits, diagnoses, procedures, drug exposures, and measurements to improve predictive performance. <p>Hyperparameter tuning (e.g., number of trees, tree depth, minimum samples per leaf) may be undertaken to optimise model performance. No deep learning architectures or foundation models will be imported into the platform. All models will be trained from scratch within the SDE.</p> <p>Provenance No externally pre-trained model weights will be ingressed. The model architecture will be implemented using established open-source machine learning libraries. All training will occur within the secure environment using approved data.</p> <p>Licensing and Intellectual Property The developed model artefacts will be specific to this project. There is no immediate commercialisation intent; however, intellectual property relating to the modelling approach may remain with the research team or sponsoring organisation, subject to governance approval.</p> <p>General Risk Characteristics of the Model Family Ensemble tree-based models can capture detailed patterns in data and may, if overfitted, memorise rare or distinctive combinations of features. The richer feature configuration increases model expressiveness and predictive power but may also increase the risk of overfitting to infrequent clinical profiles. These characteristics will be considered during training and evaluation.</p>
<p>Describe the input data your model requires and the outputs you expect it to produce.</p> <p><i>Please explain the types of input data needed to train or fine-tune the model, including the level of specificity to individuals and any plans to suppress or transform rare or identifying values. How many data points are required? Describe the structure and type of model outputs (e.g., numeric predictions, risk scores, text). If your outputs could potentially reveal sensitive</i></p>	<p>Input Data</p> <p>The model will require structured, de-identified, patient-level data derived from routinely collected clinical records within the SDE. Input variables will include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demographic attributes (e.g., age, sex) • Aggregated counts of healthcare utilisation (e.g., number of visits) • Aggregated counts of recorded diagnoses

<p><i>information, please detail how this risk will be managed.</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aggregated counts of procedures • Aggregated counts of drug exposures • Aggregated counts of clinical measurements <p>All features will be derived at the person level. Direct identifiers (e.g., names, NHS numbers, addresses) will not be used. However, aggregated clinical counts may reflect complex or rare patterns of healthcare utilisation.</p> <p>The anticipated cohort size is expected to include several tens of thousands of individuals to support robust model development and validation. Adequate sample size is required to ensure statistical stability and allow stratified splitting of the data into training and test sets.</p> <p>Outputs</p> <p>The model will produce:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A binary classification indicating predicted presence or absence of diabetes • A continuous probability score representing estimated risk <p>The probability outputs may be used to derive performance metrics such as AUC, sensitivity, specificity, and calibration measures.</p> <p>Potential Disclosure Considerations</p> <p>Although the model does not output direct identifiers, potential risks include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High-confidence probability predictions for rare clinical profiles • Overfitting to distinctive combinations of aggregated features • Indirect inference about small subgroups if model outputs are released without appropriate controls <p>These risks will be considered prior to any model egress and in line with SDE governance requirements.</p>
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<p>Summarise your approach to data processing, creating training and test data, and data cleaning.</p> <p><i>Please describe how you will preprocess and clean the data, including approaches to handling missingness or errors. Explain how you will construct training, validation, and test datasets and ensure robust separation between them. Will you use cross-validation? Please also outline any processes to detect and prevent data leakage, such as checks for duplicated individuals or near-duplicate records across dataset splits. Describe how you will identify and minimise bias in the training and test data, and whether the pipeline applies suppression or obfuscation of rare values.</i></p>	<p>Data preprocessing will include standard data quality checks to ensure completeness and logical consistency of demographic and aggregated clinical variables. This will include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Validation of demographic variable ranges • Handling missing values through appropriate exclusion or simple imputation strategies where required • Verification that aggregated feature counts are logically consistent • Features will be derived at the person level by aggregating counts of healthcare visits, diagnoses, procedures, drug exposures, and measurements. These transformations reduce direct identifiability but retain clinically meaningful variation. <p>The dataset will be partitioned into training and test sets using a stratified split to preserve outcome prevalence across partitions. Each individual will appear in only one split to prevent data leakage.</p> <p>Given the expected imbalance in diabetes prevalence, class imbalance will be assessed. If imbalance materially affects performance, class weighting or resampling techniques may be applied within the training set to improve sensitivity for minority cases.</p> <p>Aggregated feature engineering may result in rare or low-frequency combinations of clinical characteristics. No suppression of rare feature patterns is currently planned at this stage, as preserving predictive signal is a priority for model development.</p>
<p>Summarise your approach to model training, including training duration, intensity, and safeguards against memorisation of sensitive data.</p> <p><i>Please describe the structure of your training regime (e.g., number of epochs, batch size, learning-rate schedules) and how these choices balance performance with generalisation. Explain how you will monitor for overfitting during training and whether you will conduct memorisation or extraction-resistance testing. Describe any checks for duplicated or near-identical records that could encourage memorisation. What methods will you use to</i></p>	<p>The modelling approach will use ensemble tree-based classifiers trained on aggregated person-level features. Model training will involve fitting the ensemble to the training dataset and evaluating predictive performance on a held-out test dataset.</p> <p>The richer feature configuration increases model expressiveness by incorporating multiple aggregated clinical domains. While this may improve predictive accuracy, it may also increase the risk of learning highly specific patterns associated with rare or distinctive clinical profiles.</p> <p>Model complexity will be governed by predefined parameters (e.g., number of trees, minimum samples per leaf). No formal differential privacy mechanism is planned at this stage.</p>

<p><i>minimise the risk of the model learning or retaining rare or identifying values (e.g., regularisation, noise injection, differential privacy, early stopping)?</i></p>	<p>Overfitting will be monitored by comparing training and test performance. Significant divergence between training and test results would indicate potential overfitting and prompt parameter adjustment.</p> <p>Given that probability outputs will be generated, there is a potential risk that highly confident predictions could reflect memorisation of distinctive patterns. This risk will be reviewed prior to any model egress.</p> <p>Duplicate or near-identical records will be assessed during preprocessing to reduce the likelihood of reinforcing specific patterns.</p>
<p>Summarise your plan to ensure the trained model is accurate, robust and capable or delivering the stated benefits?</p> <p><i>Please describe your model testing strategy and evaluation strategy, including the metrics, benchmarks and validation datasets, any robustness or fairness assessments. Please provide information about the base model(s) including provenance and groups involved in their creation; training method and tuning approach (if different from what is described above); parameter count; published performance metrics (if any exist). Explain how you will ensure the model remains generalisable and avoids overfitting during any further finetuning stages. Also provide information about where the base model has been sourced from, how it was tuned and what group(s) was involved in creating it. How many parameters has the base model been trained on? What performance benchmarks exist for the proposed base model(s). Describe your plans to avoid the model overfitting to the training data.</i></p>	<p>Model performance will be evaluated using a held-out test dataset that is independent from the training data. The following metrics will be assessed:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Area Under the ROC Curve (AUC) • Sensitivity and specificity • Precision and recall • Calibration of predicted probabilities <p>Performance on the training and test sets will be compared to assess potential overfitting. A substantial gap between training and test performance would indicate the need for parameter adjustment.</p> <p>The model will be evaluated across key demographic subgroups (e.g., age bands, sex) to assess whether predictive performance differs materially across groups.</p> <p>Feature importance measures derived from the ensemble model may be examined to understand dominant predictors. These will be reviewed to ensure that no single rare feature disproportionately drives predictions</p> <p>Model parameter settings will be documented and retained for reproducibility. Any subsequent parameter adjustments will be recorded to ensure auditability.</p> <p>No automated model deployment is planned without governance review.</p>
<p>Describe your own assessment of any disclosure or privacy risks associated with your approach?</p> <p><i>Please describe any disclosure or other risks associated with your model and your plan to mitigate these risks to ensure the public benefit described in your data access request form is</i></p>	<p>This project involves training a person-level predictive model using aggregated clinical and demographic features. While direct identifiers are not used, potential disclosure risks remain.</p> <p>The primary privacy risks identified include:</p>

<p><i>realised without compromising the privacy of the individuals whose data is used to train the model.</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overfitting and memorisation risk: Ensemble tree-based models may learn highly specific combinations of features, particularly when rich aggregated variables are used. • Rare subgroup exposure: Individuals with unusual or low-frequency clinical profiles may contribute disproportionately to specific decision paths within the model. • Probability output sensitivity: Highly confident probability scores may indirectly reveal information about distinctive patterns within the dataset. • Membership inference risk: It may be theoretically possible to test whether a specific individual's data was included in model training by analysing model outputs. <p>These risks are considered to represent a potential medium privacy risk, particularly under the richer feature configuration.</p> <p>Mitigation strategies will include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monitoring for overfitting by comparing training and test performance • Reviewing model complexity parameters • Evaluating whether probability outputs should be restricted, rounded, or otherwise controlled prior to egress • Subjecting any model artefact to formal disclosure review prior to release <p>The public benefit of improved diabetes risk prediction must be balanced against the risk of unintended disclosure. No model artefact will be released without governance approval.</p>
<p>Summarise your ingress, egress and ongoing hosting plans for the trained model and any accompanying artefacts.</p> <p><i>Please describe what if any data or model components you will need to ingress into the TRE and then model components or additional information you will need to egress from the TRE, and whether any associated artefacts</i></p>	<p>No externally trained models or proprietary weights will be ingressed into the Secure Data Environment. All modelling will be conducted within the approved environment using authorised libraries.</p> <p>Potential egress items may include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Model performance summary statistics (aggregated metrics)

<p><i>represent a disclosure risk and how you plan to mitigate those risks. Explain where the model will be hosted long-term, how it will be licensed or distributed, and what access controls will be applied. Describe how you will manage future querying of the model to prevent misuse or leakage of sensitive information the model may have been exposed to.</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Documentation of model architecture and parameters • The trained model object (subject to governance review) <p>If a model object is proposed for egress, it will undergo formal disclosure control assessment to evaluate potential privacy risks associated with memorisation or extraction.</p> <p>No raw patient-level data will be exported</p> <p>Hosting of any approved model artefact outside the SDE will comply with institutional governance requirements and will not permit unrestricted public querying without appropriate safeguards. Access to the model will be restricted to authorised users in line with data governance policies.</p>
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Appendix 2 – AI Risk Assessment form

VISTA AI RISK ASSESSMENT TOOLKIT (Version 1)

This form supports the assessment of risks for projects intending to train a machine learning (ML) model within the Trusted Research Environment (TRE) using sensitive data. Following completion of the Researcher AI Questionnaire, this form should be completed during feasibility review to identify privacy risks and appropriate controls.

For each question, the reviewer will:

- **Assess the level of disclosure risk** associated with the proposed ML training activity.
- **Assign a risk rating:**
 - **Low** – minimal or no disclosure risk
 - **Medium** – some disclosure risk with clear, actionable mitigations
 - **High** – very high disclosure risk; egress unlikely under the current plan
- **Provide a holistic review**, considering whether combined evidence across questions changes the overall risk.
- **Review the model in the context of the egressed model register**, identifying any additional secondary disclosure risks based on previously trained models.

These answers, along with your summary, will form part of the **Data Access Committee (DAC) approval process**, ensuring ML training on sensitive data is carried out safely, responsibly, and in line with governance expectations.

All sections of this form are mandatory, if a given section is not relevant to a particular application please explain why and mark the risk as low.

This assessment should be **completed in conversation with the researchers**, providing an opportunity to:

- Explain our view of the risks
- Support them to adjust their plans where needed to better balance research benefit with privacy protection

Table instructions

Answer Summary	<i>Review and summarise the researchers answer</i>
Identified Risks	<i>List any risks inherent in the proposed plan. Include both risks identified by the research and risks you assess to be present</i>
Proposed mitigations and controls	<i>List any proposed controls or mitigations that should be requested based on the assessed risks. This should be considered independently of recommendations base on any other question.</i>
Risk rating	Low Medium High

1. Model class and type

Considerations: *The model class proposed for training on sensitive data is a major driver of disclosure risk. Reviewers should assess the model type in line with MLR01, MLR02, MLR05 and MLR06, focusing on whether the architecture is prone to memorising or explicitly storing training data, and whether it is sufficiently explainable to*

allow meaningful inspection of outputs. Consider whether the model supports empirical disclosure risk assessment, including compatibility with SACRO-ML simulated privacy attacks, as some architectures limit the ability to test for leakage. Evaluate any inherent privacy risks associated with the model class, for example, generative models, nearest neighbour approaches or large embedding models, and whether synthetic or anonymised data could reduce risk. Assess whether the model remains static after egress or if it adapts over time, as ongoing learning can alter its risk profile. Finally, identify whether additional actionable controls are needed, particularly in the areas of Safe People and Safe Settings. These may include enhanced role-based access controls, accredited hosting environments, or tighter restrictions on post-egress model use where the model class presents elevated privacy concerns.

Answer Summary	
Identified Risks	
Proposed mitigations and controls	
Risk rating	Low Medium High

2. Model input and output data

Considerations: The input and output data choices impact risks associated with membership and attribute inference MLR03 and MLR04. Considering the data schema does the application form supply? What patterns does the model apply to inputs? How clear and specific are the inputs? How will outputs be presented? How large is the input data set? To what extent does the output represent actual input data (i.e. has the model taken anything fundamental from input data). Does the presented input and output data require additional review to minimise disclosure risk in the output data. Is there a risk of rare events in the input data which increases the risk that the trained model could be used for membership or attribute inference attacks. The primary actionable controls around input and output will be based in Safe Data and Safe Output considerations including disclosure risks associated with both inputs and outputs.

Answer Summary	
Identified Risks	
Proposed mitigations and controls	
Risk rating	Low Medium High

3. Data processing

Considerations: The data processing choices impact risks associated with membership and attribute inference MLR03 and MLR04. Does the pipeline have data privacy checks such as checks for data leakage such as patient duplication across test and train data. Does the pipeline ensure the training data does not contain quasi-identifiers. Does the pipeline ensure suppression or obfuscation of rare values. Does the pipeline assess potential bias and does the plan include mitigations to minimise any bias present in the data? Should the plan be extended to include protections for data leakage or bias in the training data The primary actionable controls around data processing will be based in Safe Data considerations such as having sufficient steps in place to minimise the risk of rare events in the training data or data leakage between training and test data.

Answer Summary	
Identified Risks	
Proposed mitigations and controls	
Risk rating	Low Medium High

4. Model training plan

Considerations: *The training plan choices can impact how likely the model is to capture precise details of individuals in the dataset, this will primarily focus on risks MRL01 and MRL05. Consider how much detail was provided about the proposed model training plan. Has the researcher described how they balance the model performance with generalisation. Have they described mitigations about model memorisation or other disclosure risks. Do requirements need to be proposed for the training plan to minimise it introducing any disclosure risk? Should any controls with respect to model training need to be added to the Data Access Agreement. The primary actionable controls for risks associated with the training plan will be based in Safe Data and Safe Settings such as ensuring the training data is minimally disclosive and the training plan as appropriate monitoring to ensure minimal overfitting*

Answer Summary	
Identified Risks	
Proposed mitigations and controls	
Risk rating	Low Medium High

5. Model quality

Considerations: *How the researchers plan to monitor and confirm model quality is primarily associated with understanding if the model can deliver the proposed public benefit and as such, with appropriate controls, any potential disclosure risks are justified. It is important to understand where has the base model been sourced from? How was it tuned? Who/what groups were involved in model creation? How many parameters has the model been trained on (depends on model type)? Is the model quantised? Has the model undergone pre SDE testing? What are the performance benchmarks for the model in use? How were weights and biases of model ‘neurons’ adjusted for accuracy (terminology depends on model type)? Does model size balance complexity with overfitting risk? How specific is the model use case? Relevant actionable controls associated with model quality will be based in Safe projects and ensuring the model quality is sufficient to deliver the proposed benefit.*

Answer Summary	
Identified Risks	
Proposed mitigations and controls	
Risk rating	Low Medium High

6. Disclosure risk management

Considerations: *The researcher’s consideration of disclosure risk management will be primarily associated with MLR03, 04 and 07. Does the plan identify and propose mitigations for any potential disclosure risks in the trained model or model outputs? Can you identify any disclosure risks not identified by the researcher in the proposal? Does the disclosure risk identified mean there are additional controls should be placed on an egressed model such as secure hosting or suitable licensing. The primary actionable controls for this risk will be in restricting model egress till project closure and proposing controls based in Safe Data and Safe Settings.*

Answer Summary	
Identified Risks	
Proposed mitigations and controls	
Risk rating	Low Medium High

7. Ingress, egress and model hosting plans

Considerations: *The focus of this assessment will be determined as much by the risk scores for the other questions as well as the ingress, egress and hosting plans. A higher risk model will need plans that already incorporate aspects of the Five-Safes such as supporting Safe Settings with secure hosting and Safe People with role-based access controls. Their to ingress any data to support their training and testing plan will need to be reviewed on the basis of what type of data they need to ingress, reference information which is available in the public domain should be considered safe but other sensitive data will require the Data Access Committee to confirm the research teams approvals to hold such data and using it in the TRE for this purpose, what other data as well as the model do they need to egress, have they indicated any disclosure risks associated with these other data. Where is the model going to be egressed to, does that increase the disclosure risk (i.e., a secure environment with limited access vs public hosting or sharing via github). Actionable controls that may be needed for this area include Safe People, Safe Settings and Safe Outputs.*

Answer Summary	
Identified Risks	
Proposed mitigations and controls	
Risk rating	Low Medium High

8. Holistic risk review

Considerations: *This is a holistic review which aims to see intersections between the different questions and understand if any of the risks need to increase or decrease because of them, such as the model type is highly likely to memorise training data but as the input data is non disclosive, this risk can be disregarded. Review all the answers combined with the dataset definition and consider if any risks emerge or disappear after considering the setup holistically, this is most likely to be at the intersection of model class, input/output data and the training plans but there may be other intersections where this could happen.*

Answer Summary	
Identified Risks	
Proposed mitigations and controls	
Risk rating	Low Medium High

9. Review against existing models

Considerations: *This plan should be compared with the TRE’s model registry to check if any already released models used very similar input and output data and could present a secondary disclosure risk*

10. Risk score summary

Add the ratings for each category to this table and colour the cell based on the following ranking *Low, Medium, High*

Category	Score
Model Class and Type	
Model Input and Outputs data	
Data Processing	
Disclosure Risk Management	
Model Quality	
Egress and Hosting Plans	
Holistic risk review	

11. Risk summary

Provide a summary of the key risks which are the basis for your recommended controls

12. Recommended controls

When summarising the recommended controls, base the final recommendation on the highest level of risk identified across all assessed questions. Although each question is evaluated independently, the overall controls should reflect the most stringent measures required by any single high risk finding. For example, if the model class is unlikely to memorise training data and therefore present low disclosure risk, but the proposed inputs and outputs are rare events which are highly disclosive, the overall recommendation may still be to implement secure hosting with strict role based access controls, assuming the public benefit is sufficient to justify proceeding.

Example AI Risk Assessment Form - Diabetes Risk Prediction Using Aggregated Clinical Features

Model class and type

Considerations: *The model class proposed for training on sensitive data is a major driver of disclosure risk. Reviewers should assess the model type in line with MLR01, MLR02, MLR05 and MLR06, focusing on whether the architecture is prone to memorising or explicitly storing training data, and whether it is sufficiently explainable to allow meaningful inspection of outputs. Consider whether the model supports empirical disclosure risk assessment, including compatibility with SACRO--ML simulated privacy attacks, as some architectures limit the ability to test for leakage. Evaluate any inherent privacy risks associated with the model class, for example, generative models, nearest neighbour approaches or large embedding models, and whether synthetic or anonymised data could reduce risk. Assess whether the model remains static after egress or if it adapts over time, as ongoing learning can alter its risk profile. Finally, identify whether -additional- actionable controls are needed, particularly in the areas of Safe People and Safe Settings. These may include enhanced role-based access controls, accredited hosting environments, or tighter restrictions on -post-egress- model use where the model class presents elevated privacy concerns.*

<p>Answer Summary</p>	<p>The project will build supervised machine learning models to predict the risk of Type 2 diabetes using routinely collected clinical data within a secure data environment. It will use ensemble tree-based methods (mainly Random Forest-style classifiers) because they handle non-linear relationships, feature interactions, and mixed data types well.</p> <p>Two versions of the model are planned:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • a baseline model using demographic and limited clinical summaries • a richer model adding aggregated healthcare activity data (visits, diagnoses, procedures, medications, measurements) to improve accuracy <p>Models will be trained from scratch inside the secure environment using open-source libraries, with no external pre-trained models or deep learning systems. Hyperparameters will be tuned to optimise performance.</p> <p>The resulting models are project-specific with no immediate commercialisation plans, though intellectual property may remain with the research team or sponsor.</p> <p>A key risk is overfitting ensemble tree models may memorise rare or unique patient patterns, especially with the richer feature set, so this will be managed during training and evaluation.</p>
<p>Identified Risks</p>	<p>These risks have already been mentioned in the summary</p> <p>Overfitting and memorisation of patterns Distinctive combinations of aggregated clinical features creating indirect identifiability. Sharing individual risk scores or exporting the model outside the secure system could reveal sensitive health information.</p>

Proposed mitigations and controls	<p>Researcher has already mentioned the mitigations in the summary Overfitting risk is addressed during training and evaluation as described in the summary, so the risk is low. Keep all training and use of the model inside the secure environment</p>
Risk rating	Medium

Model input and output data

Considerations: *The input and output data choices impact risks associated with membership and attribute inference MLR03 and MLR04. Considering the data schema does the application form supply? What patterns does the model apply to inputs? How clear and specific are the inputs? How will outputs be presented? How large is the input data set? To what extent does the output represent actual input data (i.e. has the model taken anything fundamental from input data). Does the presented input and output data require additional review to minimise disclosure risk in the output data. Is there a risk of rare events in the input data which increases the risk that the trained model could be used for membership or attribute inference attacks. The primary actionable controls around input and output will be based in Safe Data and Safe Output considerations including disclosure risks associated with both inputs and outputs.*

Answer Summary	<p>Input Data De-identified, person-level data from routinely collected clinical records within the Secure Data Environment (SDE)</p> <p>Features include: Demographics (age, sex) Aggregated counts of healthcare utilisation (visits) Aggregated counts of diagnoses, procedures, drug exposures, and clinical measurements Direct identifiers (e.g., names, NHS numbers, addresses) are not used Aggregated counts may reflect rare or complex utilisation patterns Cohort size: tens of thousands to ensure robust model training, validation, and stratified train/test splitting</p> <p>Outputs Binary classification: predicted presence or absence of diabetes Continuous probability score: estimated risk Used to derive performance metrics: AUC, sensitivity, specificity, calibration</p> <p>Potential Risks High confidence probability predictions for rare or distinctive clinical profiles Overfitting to unique combinations of aggregated features Indirect inference about small subgroups if outputs are released without controls</p> <p>Risk Management Risks will be considered prior to any model egress Managed in line with SDE governance requirements</p>
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Identified Risks	<p>These risks have already been mentioned in the summary</p> <p>Indirect reference about small subgroups if outputs are shared Risk through continuous probability scores High confidence predictions for rare or distinctive profiles</p>
Proposed mitigations and controls	<p>The mitigations have already been mentioned in the summary</p> <p>Restrict output release to aggregated metrics only Aggregate or bin rare features Avoid releasing individual level predictions</p>
Risk rating	<p>Medium</p>

Data processing

Considerations: *The data processing choices impact risks associated with membership and attribute inference MLR03 and MLR04. Does the pipeline have data privacy checks such as checks for data leakage such as patient duplication across test and train data. Does the pipeline ensure the training data does not contain quasi-identifiers. Does the pipeline ensure suppression or obfuscation of rare values. Does the pipeline assess potential bias and does the plan include mitigations to minimise any bias present in the data? Should the plan be extended to include protections for data leakage or bias in the training data The primary actionable controls around data processing will be based in Safe Data considerations such as having sufficient steps in place to minimise the risk of rare events in the training data or data leakage between training and test data.*

Answer Summary	<p>Data quality checks: Ensure completeness and logical consistency of demographic and aggregated clinical variables, including range validation and handling missing values via exclusion or simple imputation.</p> <p>Aggregated feature derivation: Person-level counts of healthcare visits, diagnoses, procedures, drug exposures, and measurements; reduces direct identifiability while retaining clinically meaningful variation.</p> <p>Dataset splitting: Stratified train/test split preserves outcome prevalence; individuals appear in only one partition to prevent data leakage.</p> <p>Class imbalance handling: Diabetes prevalence imbalance will be assessed; class weighting or resampling may be applied in the training set if needed to improve sensitivity for minority cases.</p> <p>Rare feature patterns: Aggregated feature engineering may produce low-frequency combinations; currently no suppression is planned to preserve predictive signal for model development.</p>
Identified Risks	<p>Rare or low-level feature patterns increase membership/attribute inference risk as no suppression is planned.</p> <p>Potential demographic or clinical subgroup biases.</p> <p>High-dimensional quasi-identifiers.</p>
Proposed mitigations and controls	<p>Monitor and combine or bin very rare features</p> <p>Weighting and resampling for underrepresented groups</p>
Risk rating	Medium

Model training plan

Considerations: *The training plan choices can impact how likely the model is to capture precise details of individuals in the dataset, this will primarily focus on risks MRL01 and MRL05. Consider how much detail was provided about the proposed model training plan. Has the researcher described how they balance the model performance with generalisation. Have they described mitigations about model memorisation or other disclosure risks. Do requirements need to be proposed for the training plan to minimise it introducing any disclosure risk? Should any controls with respect to model training need to be added to the Data Access Agreement. The primary actionable controls for risks associated with the training plan will be based in Safe Data and Safe Settings such as ensuring the training data is minimally disclosive and the training plan as appropriate monitoring to ensure minimal overfitting*

<p>Answer Summary</p>	<p>Uses ensemble tree-based classifiers (e.g., Random Forest) trained on aggregated, person-level clinical features. Models trained on a training set and evaluated on a separate held-out test set. Richer feature set improves accuracy but increases complexity and risk of learning rare or highly specific patterns. Model complexity controlled through parameters (e.g., number of trees, minimum samples per leaf). Overfitting monitored by comparing training vs test performance and adjusting parameters if needed. Duplicate or near-identical records checked during preprocessing No formal differential privacy methods currently applied. Probability outputs may pose some memorisation risk; reviewed before any model or output leaves the secure environment.</p>
<p>Identified Risks</p>	<p>These risks have already been mentioned in the summary</p> <p>Overfitting of individuals Learning rare or distinct clinical profiles High-confidence probability outputs reflecting memorisation Lack of formal privacy-preserving methods</p>
<p>Proposed mitigations and controls</p>	<p>The mitigations have already been mentioned in the summary</p> <p>Control complexity (limit trees, minimum sample per leaf) and comparing training vs tests performance. Avoid highly granular outputs where not necessary Review outputs before release and prefer aggregated performance metrics Training within secure environment only and governance review before egress.</p>
<p>Risk rating</p>	<p>Medium</p>

Model quality

Considerations: *How the researchers plan to monitor and confirm model quality is primarily associated with understanding if the model can deliver the proposed public benefit and as such, with appropriate controls, any potential disclosure risks are justified. It is important to understand where has the base model been sourced from? How was it tuned? Who/what groups were involved in model creation? How many parameters has the model been trained on (depends on model type)? Is the model quantised? Has the model undergone pre SDE testing? What are the performance benchmarks for the model in use? How were weights and biases of model ‘neurons’ adjusted for accuracy (terminology depends on model type)? Does model size balance complexity with overfitting risk? How specific is the model use case? Relevant actionable controls associated with model quality will be based in Safe projects and ensuring the model quality is sufficient to deliver the proposed benefit.*

<p>Answer Summary</p>	<p>Model evaluated on a held-out test dataset separate from training data Performance measured using AUC, sensitivity, specificity, precision, recall, and calibration Training vs test performance compared to detect overfitting, with parameters adjusted if gaps are found Performance assessed across key demographic groups (e.g., age, sex) to check for bias or unequal accuracy</p>
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	<p>Feature importance reviewed to ensure no single rare feature disproportionately drives predictions</p> <p>Model parameters documented for reproducibility and auditability</p> <p>No deployment or release without governance review</p>
Identified Risks	<p>These risks have already been mentioned in the summary</p> <p>Overfitting leading to memorisation</p> <p>Poor generalisation reducing public benefit</p> <p>Bias or unequal performance across groups</p> <p>A single rare diagnosis or feature could dominate decisions</p>
Proposed mitigations and controls	<p>The mitigations have already been mentioned in the summary</p> <p>Compare training vs tests performance</p> <p>Multiple performance metrics and bench marking on the test data Review subgroup differences and adjust if needed</p> <p>Check that rare features are not overly influential</p> <p>No automated deployment</p>
Risk rating	Medium

Disclosure risk management

Considerations: *The researcher's consideration of disclosure risk management will be primarily associated with MLR03, 04 and 07. Does the plan identify and propose mitigations for any potential disclosure risks in the trained model or model outputs? Can you identify any disclosure risks not identified by the researcher in the proposal? Does the disclosure risk identified mean there are additional controls should be placed on an egressed model such as secure hosting or suitable licensing. The primary actionable controls for this risk will be in restricting model egress till project closure and proposing controls based in Safe Data and Safe Settings.*

Answer Summary	<p>Project Overview</p> <p>Training a person-level predictive model using aggregated clinical and demographic features</p> <p>Direct identifiers are not used, but some privacy risks remain</p> <p>Key Privacy Risks</p> <p>Overfitting / memorisation: Model may learn highly specific feature combinations, especially with rich aggregated data</p> <p>Rare subgroup exposure: Individuals with unusual or low-frequency clinical profiles may disproportionately influence predictions</p> <p>Probability output sensitivity: Confident probability scores could reveal information about distinctive patterns</p> <p>Membership inference: It may be possible to test if a specific individual's data was in the training set</p> <p>Mitigation Strategies</p> <p>Compare training vs test performance to monitor overfitting</p>
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	Review and control model complexity parameters Restrict, round, or control probability outputs before release Subject all model artefacts to formal disclosure review prior to release Governance approval required before any model or output is released
Identified Risks	The risks have already been mentioned in the summary.
Proposed mitigations and controls	The mitigations have already been mentioned in the summary
Risk rating	Medium

Ingress, egress and model hosting plans

Considerations: *The focus of this assessment will be determined as much by the risk scores for the other questions as well as the ingress, egress and hosting plans. A higher risk model will need plans that already incorporate aspects of the Five-Safes such as supporting Safe Settings with secure hosting and Safe People with role-based access controls. Their to ingress any data to support their training and testing plan will need to be reviewed on the basis of what type of data they need to ingress, reference information which is available in the public domain should be considered safe but other sensitive data will require the Data Access Committee to confirm the research teams approvals to hold such data and using it in the TRE for this purpose, what other data as well as the model do they need to egress, have they indicated any disclosure risks associated with these other data. Where is the model going to be egressed to, does that increase the disclosure risk (i.e . a secure environment with limited access vs public hosting or sharing via github) . Actionable controls that may be needed for this area include Safe People, Safe Settings and Safe Outputs.*

Answer Summary	<p>Model Environment and Governance All modelling conducted within the Secure Data Environment (SDE) using authorised libraries No externally trained models or proprietary weights will be imported</p> <p>Potential Outputs / Egress Aggregated model performance metrics (AUC, sensitivity, etc.) Documentation of model architecture and parameters Trained model object (only after governance review and disclosure assessment)</p> <p>Privacy and Access Controls Formal disclosure review of any model object before egress to assess risks of memorisation or extraction No raw patient-level data will be exported Hosting or use outside the SDE must comply with institutional governance Access restricted to authorised users; no unrestricted public querying allowed</p>
Identified Risks	
Proposed mitigations and controls	
Risk rating	Low

Holistic risk review

Considerations: *This is a holistic review which aims to see intersections between the different questions and understand if any of the risks need to increase or decrease because of them, such as the model type is highly likely to memorise training data but as the input data is non-disclosive, this risk is scan be removed. Review all the answers combined with the dataset definition and consider if any risks emerge or disappear after considering the setup holistically, this is most likely to be at the intersection of model class, input/output data and the training plans but there may be other intersections where this could happen.*

<p>Answer Summary</p>	<p>Supervised ensemble tree-based classifiers (Random Forest-style). Two configurations: baseline (demographics + limited clinical data) and richer (adds aggregated healthcare features). Controlled complexity via parameters (trees, minimum samples per leaf). No deep learning or external pre-trained models. Validate data, handle missing values, ensure logical consistency Aggregate features at person level (visits, diagnoses, procedures, drugs, measurements). Stratified train/test split; each individual in only one set. Assess class imbalance and apply weighting/resampling if needed. Inputs: de-identified demographics and aggregated clinical counts; no direct identifiers. Outputs: binary diabetes prediction, probability scores, aggregated performance metrics. Training entirely in Secure Data Environment (SDE). Overfitting monitored via training/test comparison; parameters adjusted if needed. Duplicate/near-identical records checked. No formal differential privacy applied. Governance review required before any output leaves SDE. Evaluate AUC, sensitivity, specificity, precision, recall, calibration. Assess performance across demographic subgroups. Feature importance reviewed to avoid rare feature dominance. Document parameters and adjustments for reproducibility. No automated deployment without governance review. Risks: overfitting/memorisation, membership inference, high-confidence probability outputs, subgroup bias. Mitigations: monitor overfitting, control complexity, review probability outputs, formal disclosure review, governance approval. No external pre-trained models or proprietary weights. Egress: aggregated metrics, model documentation, or trained model object (after disclosure review). No raw patient-level data exported. All access governed by institutional policies. Hosting outside SDE follows governance rules. Access restricted to authorised users; no public querying. Safe Data and Safe Output policies applied.</p>
<p>Identified Risks</p>	<p>overfitting/memorisation, membership inference, high-confidence probability outputs, subgroup bias</p>
<p>Proposed mitigations and controls</p>	<p>monitor overfitting, control complexity, review probability outputs, formal disclosure review, governance approval</p>

Risk rating	Medium
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Review against existing models

Considerations: *This plan should be compared with the TRE’s model registry to check if any already released models used very similar input and output data and could present a secondary disclosure risk*

There are no other models currently on the register

Risk score summary

Add the ratings for each category to this table and colour the cell based on the following ranking *Low, Medium, High*

Category	Score
Model Class and Type	Medium
Model Input and Outputs data	Medium
Data Processing	Medium
Disclosure Risk Management	Medium
Model Quality	Medium
Egress and Hosting Plans	Low
Holistic risk review	Medium

Risk summary

Provide a summary of the key risks which are the basis for your recommended controls

The model uses de-identified, person-level clinical and demographic data; however, privacy risks remain due to the use of detailed aggregated healthcare features and person-level modelling.

Key risks include:

- **Overfitting or memorisation:** where the ensemble model may learn highly specific or rare patient patterns
- **Membership inference:** where it may be possible to test whether a specific individual’s data was used in training
- **High-confidence probability outputs:** which could indirectly reveal distinctive clinical profiles
- **Rare or small subgroups:** which may increase re-identification or attribute inference risk
- **Potential subgroup bias:** where uneven performance could disproportionately affect certain demographic groups

Overall, risks arise primarily from model complexity and detailed feature combinations rather than direct identifiers.

Recommended controls

When summarising the recommended controls, base the final recommendation on the highest level of risk identified across all assessed questions. Although each question is evaluated independently, the overall controls should reflect the most stringent measures required by any single high risk finding. For example, if the model class is unlikely to memorise training data and therefore present low disclosure risk, but the proposed inputs and outputs are rare events which are highly disclosive, the overall recommendation may still be to implement secure hosting with strict role based access controls, assuming the public benefit is sufficient to justify proceeding.

Controls should reflect a medium disclosure risk profile and prioritise safe handling of model artefacts and outputs:

- Train and evaluate models only within the Secure Data Environment (SDE)
- Monitor and minimise overfitting through training/test comparisons and complexity limits
- Use feature aggregation and avoid releasing rare or highly specific outputs
- Review and, where necessary, round, restrict, or suppress probability outputs prior to egress
- Conduct formal disclosure control assessment of any model artefact before release
- Export aggregated metrics only by default; no raw patient-level data
- Apply secure hosting and role-based access controls for any approved external model use
- Require governance approval and auditability for all egress and deployment

Appendix 3 - Released Trained Model Registry

VISTA AI RISK ASSESSMENT TOOLKIT (Version 1)

GRAIMATTER recommends that a TRE must keep a record³ of every ML model trained on the data they allow to be egressed from their environment. This facilitates two different goals, the first is transparency, this information can be added to the Data Use Registry¹⁵ ensuring all interested parties can understand the projects, research outputs and planned public benefits from any TRE project. It also allows the TRE to assess any risk of secondary disclosure between models when approving new ML projects and ensure appropriate actionable controls are put in place, secondary disclosure risk between models can be anticipated and managed.

For each model egressed, the registry should capture the following information

Attribute	Description
Project code ⁱ	TRE project identifier
Project name ⁱ	Title of the project
Purpose and benefit of model ⁱ	A terse summary of the purpose the model has been trained for and the benefit that purpose enables
Model class ⁱ	The broad class of ML model trained in the TRE
Model input ⁱ	What input data attributes was used to train the model and will be used to query the model
Model output ⁱ	What data attributes or scores will be output by the model after a query
Summary of training data processing ⁱ	A terse summary of how the data was cleaned and processed before model training and validation
Data processing code archive	A code archive for the data processing pipeline
Model validation results ⁱ	A summary of the model validation results
SACRO-ML privacy attack results	A summary of the SACRO-ML results
License text ⁱ	A summary of the license conditions and a pointer to an archive of the full license text
Summary of any additional controls from the Data Access Agreement (DAA) ⁱ	A summary of any additional controls placed on the model such as secure hosting with role-based access-control and/or query limitations and a pointer to an archive to the full DAA text
Hosting location for egressed model ⁱ	Information about where the egressed model is hosted for reuse, this can vary and include a github repository or another TRE which provides hosting for ML models trained on sensitive data depending on the agreed controls for the model.

i: Fields which should be published as part of the Data Use Register²³ on project closure. The code archive is an internal location which would not be accessible to external parties so not needed to be included in the Data Use Registry

Example Released trained model registry - Diabetes Risk Prediction Using Aggregated Clinical Features

Attribute	Description
Project code ⁱ	TRE-ML-001
Project name ⁱ	Diabetes Risk Prediction Using Aggregated Clinical Features
Purpose and benefit of model ⁱ	The model is designed to predict the likelihood of Type 2 diabetes using routinely collected clinical data. The intended benefit is to support population-level risk stratification and early identification of individuals at higher risk, enabling improved clinical decision-making and preventative care planning.
Model class ⁱ	Supervised machine learning – ensemble tree-based classifier (Random Forest)
Model input ⁱ	Person-level, de-identified, structured features derived from clinical records, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demographic attributes (e.g., age band, sex) • Aggregated counts of healthcare visits • Aggregated counts of diagnoses • Aggregated counts of procedures • Aggregated counts of drug exposures • Aggregated counts of clinical measurements
Model output ⁱ	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Binary classification (diabetes / no diabetes) • Predicted probability score representing risk of diabetes
Summary of training data processing ⁱ	Data was cleaned and pre-processed through validation of demographic variables, handling of missing values, and aggregation of clinical events into person-level feature counts. The dataset was split into stratified training and test sets to preserve outcome distribution. Duplicate and inconsistent records were checked and removed prior to modelling.
Data processing code archive	Code used for data preprocessing and model training is maintained within the secure project repository inside the TRE environment and is version-controlled.
Model validation results ⁱ	Model performance was evaluated on a held-out test dataset. Metrics assessed included AUC, sensitivity, specificity, precision, and F1-score. Results indicated moderate predictive performance with no significant overfitting observed between training and test datasets.
SACRO-ML privacy attack results	Simulated privacy attacks were conducted to assess potential disclosure risks, including membership inference scenarios. Results indicated low to moderate vulnerability under baseline conditions, with risk increasing under richer feature configurations. These findings informed the application of model controls prior to egress.
License text ⁱ	
Summary of any additional controls from the Data Access Agreement (DAA) ⁱ	Access to the model is restricted to authorised users within approved environments. Controls include role-based access restrictions, prohibition of unrestricted public querying, and requirement for disclosure review prior to any redistribution or reuse. Model outputs

	may be subject to precision control (e.g., probability rounding) where required.
Hosting location for egressed model ⁱ	The model will be hosted within a Trusted Research Environment (TRE) and subject to governance controls prior to any potential deployment within secure clinical environments.